

Non-equilibrium Thermodynamic Studies of Electrokinetic Effects. Part-XXII. Onsagar's Reciprocity Relations

R. L. BLOKHRA*, S. K. AGARWAL and (Mrs.) NEERJA ARORA

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005

Manuscript received 12 October 1988, revised 16 June 1989, accepted 19 June 1989

Onsagar's reciprocity relations have been verified from the studies on electro-osmosis and the streaming potential of multicomponent solutions (ethylene glycol + acetonitrile + dimethylformamide) at 40° across a sintered pyrex glass disc.

THE thermodynamic theory of irreversible processes is essentially based on three conditions, viz. (i) linear phenomenological laws, (ii) the validity of Onsagar's reciprocity relations, and (iii) phenomenological coefficients may be treated as constants, of course, in addition to the validity of Gibbs' formula for entropy production. In most physical processes, the above assumptions are not true in general.

Rastogi *et al.*¹⁻⁵ and Blokhra *et al.*⁶⁻¹¹ showed that linear relations between forces and fluxes do not hold beyond a certain magnitude of the force used to generate the flux. These workers also proved that phenomenological constants should not be treated as constants because these coefficients vary when the force exceeds a certain magnitude and the above mentioned conditions hold only in a limited region. The purpose of the present work is to test Onsagar's reciprocity relations through the studies on electro-osmosis and the streaming potential of an isodielectric multicomponent solution (EG + ACN (70%) + DMF (30%)) across a sintered pyrex glass disc.

Experimental

Dimethylformamide and acetonitrile were purified as described earlier^{7,8}. Ethylene glycol was purified by vacuum distillation after drying it over calcium oxide, calcium sulphate and sodium metal and stored in sealed bottles. The apparatus used and the experimental procedure for studying electro-osmosis were similar to those described earlier⁶. For streaming potential measurements, constant pressure-head was maintained⁹ with a reservoir and the liquid was allowed to flow freely through the pyrex sintered glass. The pressure difference was measured with a cathetometer. The streaming potential was measured with an electrometer supplied by the Electronic Corporation of India.

Results and Discussion

According to the thermodynamic theory of irreversible processes, the phenomenological equa-

tions for describing the volume flow and current flow in case of electrokinetic effect are written as¹²

$$I = L_{11} \Delta\phi + L_{12} \Delta P \quad (1)$$

$$J = L_{21} \Delta\phi + L_{22} \Delta P \quad (2)$$

where the L 's are phenomenological coefficients with $L_{21} = L_{12}$ according to Onsagar's theorem. L_{11} is related to resistance while L_{12} is related to the permeability of the liquid. The coefficients L_{12} and L_{21} are the cross-phenomenological coefficients and have their usual significance.

Now Onsagar's reciprocity relation is

$$L_{21} = L_{12} \quad (3)$$

For verification of the relation (3), evaluation of L_{12} and L_{21} has to be carried out by different methods. The evaluation of L_{12} is carried out from the streaming potential measurements, as described below.

Since at $I = 0$, relation (1) becomes

$$\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta P}\right)_{I=0} = \frac{L_{12}}{L_{11}} \quad (4)$$

and at $\Delta P = 0$, relation (1) becomes

$$I = L_{11} \Delta\phi \quad (5)$$

L_{11} can be expressed by the relation,

$$L_{11} = 1/R \quad (6)$$

where R is the resistance of the electro-osmotic cell. From equations (4) and (6), it follows that

$$\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta P}\right)_{I=0} = L_{12} R \quad (7)$$

The values of $\Delta\phi$, corresponding to different values of the pressure difference (ΔP) across the disc were measured with an electrometer. The right-hand-side of equation (7) was estimated from the slope of the straight line plots of $\Delta\phi$ vs ΔP

for different systems and on substituting, the value of R , L_{12} was estimated.

The phenomenological coefficients L_{21} was estimated from the electro-osmosis experiment described earlier⁶. The values of L_{12} and L_{21} for the different mixtures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF CROSS-PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS L_{12} AND L_{21} FOR EG IN ACN (70%)—DMF (30%) MIXTURES AT 40°

Percentage of % EG (w/w)	L_{12} $\times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ AJ}^{-1}$	L_{21} $\times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ AJ}^{-1}$
0	6.71	7.10
5	2.83	2.90
7.5	5.28	5.35
10	3.08	3.25

From Table 1, it is observed that the values of L_{12} are in good agreement with those of L_{21} for the various mixtures. This proves that the Onsager's reciprocity relation, $L_{12} = L_{21}$, holds good for electrokinetic effects in the isodielectric mixtures

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.K.A.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Post-Doctoral Fellowship.

References

1. R. P. RASTOGI, R. L. BLOKHRA and R. K. AGGARWAL, *Trans., Faraday Soc.*, 1964, 60, 1386.
2. R. P. RASTOGI and R. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Physica*, 1961, 27, 265.
3. R. P. RASTOGI and R. M. JHA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 1017.
4. R. P. RASTOGI, K. SINGH and M. L. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 46.
5. R. P. RASTOGI and K. M. JHA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, 62, 585.
6. R. L. BLOKHRA, C. L. KAUL, B. R. SONI and S. K. JALOTO, *Electrochim Acta*, 1967, 12, 773.
7. R. L. BLOKHRA and T. C. SINGHAL, *J. Electroana. Chem.*, 1974, 57, 19.
8. R. L. BLOKHRA, S. K. AGARWAL and N. ARORA, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1980, 73, 88.
9. R. L. BLOKHRA and S. S. THAKUR, *J. Non-Equilib. Thermodyn.*, 1982, 7, 145.
10. R. L. BLOKHRA, M. L. PARMAR and S. S. THAKUR, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1984, 21, 123.
11. R. L. BLOKHRA, S. KUMAR and N. UPADHYAY, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1988, 33, 347.
12. I. PRIGOGINE, "Introduction to Thermodynamics of Irreversible Process", Charles C. Thomas, Springfield III, 1955.